

CONTEXT MEANING IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT: It is known that archaeologists have found and studied many stone words, that is, texts, and this process is still going on. From this we can clearly say that text and textology in Linguistics did not appear today or yesterday, it has been an active source of written information in linguistics and other fields. In this article, we will consider the results of the study of how the text and textology entered our language and until today.

Keywords: Text, minimal text, maximal text, narrative text, visual text, explanatory text, didactic text, informative text,

In today's era of globalization, it is natural that every nation, every independent state should prioritize the issue of securing its national interests, first of all, preserving and developing its culture, ancient values, and native language" [1]. And we, as the inheritors of the priceless wealth passed down from our ancestors to our generations, consider preserving our mother tongue, enriching it, and increasing its prestige as the most important, long-lasting goal for us, and the importance of this issue should never be overlooked. Text linguistics has become one of the important branches of linguistics during the last decades. This is certainly not in vain. Because the main task of linguistics is to find out the phenomena that exist in a particular language and the laws of their operation.

It is valuable about the rich scientific and spiritual heritage, literature, and art of our people information is reflected in the manuscript sources written in Arabic script. Manuscript learning examples based on the original, students from the sources of Arabic spelling informing, training them as specialists in the higher education system culturally causes an increase in educational level. Publication of classic sources based on manuscript copies, excellent scientific annotations, preparation of their critical text, conducting new scientific and theoretical research in the field of textual studies today is one of the urgent issues. Cover style and handwriting for this to achieve high results by working based on the experience of working on the text possible in the process of studying the method of textual studies, especially the history of the text it is necessary to pay special attention to the following important features during implementation: 1) The only goal of scholars is to restore a perfect text free of errors teamwork; 2) comparing the text letter by letter, word by word; 3) to

eliminate errors, the experts prepare the texts with each other cross-examination with; 4) without erasing the errors in the text drawing; 5) a master scholar before taking a lesson on the restored reliable text if written permission was given by, today the Society of Textologists to issue a special permit.

There is the essence of the text in Uzbek linguistics, the means of its formation, and also many works dedicated to the study of issues related to text components. Academician G. Abdurakhmanov[10] was in Tashkent on September 10-12, 1980 about the text at the III conference of Turkic scholars of the former Union he expressed his thoughts and distinguished a number of text types. A. Gulomov "Current Uzbek literary language. Textbook "Syntax" (with M. Askarova in cooperation) for his thoughts on the text during the preparation of the third edition had written it down. The content of the scholarly work is fully formed in this work emphasizes that it can be understood only from the text, and the completeness of the thought in the sentence has a relative character:

"1. Expression of opinion is only within the scope of the sentence (simple sentence and compound sentence). A syntactic whole, which is usually larger than a sentence, gives the complete idea. The word is one of its components in the composition of the whole.

2. This is a component different from other components of the whole in all respects (content, grammar). His own composition and style properties will be saved.

3. A simple sentence in the composition of the whole under certain conditions can form a paragraph by itself..

4. Such a syntactic whole, syntactic construction is considered text. A separate sentence represents a relatively complete thought, text means the content of a whole complex.

5. Since the text is a whole, it may also have some headings to match its content. The text is divided into some segments - parts (individual fragments, paragraphs, sentences) divided). Therefore, the text is even more clear that language is a means of communication shows. Speech appears as text.

6. Text - a large speech fragment, paragraph, and a piece of text. All text views (max text and min text) fully represent a certain topic (content). So, it is a high level syntactic unit.

In today's linguistics, the text is interpreted as a separate large unit of the language (super syntactic whole) and the main object of the field called text linguistics. When studying the text, it is said that it should be distinguished from the phrase and the sentence and that the text has a few categories and laws. The

linguist M.X.Hakimov writes about this in his dissertation work on scientific text research: In the dictionary meaning of the word text, there are concepts of connection and connection, therefore, studying the connection of text content with the help of some connectors has become one of the main problems of the field of "Text Linguistics". Repetition expressing the interconnection of text units and their several appearances, some words related to the pronoun group, and the functions of the appearance of the sentence in the form of the interrogative form in text formation has a special place in text linguistics. In this work, the author emphasizes that the term "text" should be distinguished from other linguistic terms such as "speech", and "context". Speech is manifested in oral and written forms. The written form of the speech corresponds to the content expressed by the text term. "Speech is a speech activity directed from the subject to the addressee. And the text is not only objective information but also the material appearance of the speech, which also includes pragmatic content.

The linguist scientist M.Arriv says "Text is the whole that brings out discourse, expression (recit), and the connection between them." In scientific literature, the term context is indicated as a product of the speech situation. "Context is a minimal unit of speech, presented to clarify the meaning or concept expressed on the basis of a lexical or grammatical unit. As a rule, this combination of words, sometimes a sentence, rarely equals a paragraph or a whole text. Almost all linguists who use the word "text" try to define this concept in one way or another. The text is a device with a multifaceted, complex structure, therefore, its characteristic semiotic, communicative, structural, pragmatic, cognitive, and nominative features should be taken into account when describing it. But each researcher usually focuses on the aspects that interest him, as a result, the given definition will not be perfect, or detailed. In other words, no definition can perfectly describe a phenomenon as complex as a text. Therefore, each researcher or group of researchers has a unique point of view on the text phenomenon, and the planned research is subordinated to this point of view.

It is difficult to strongly object to any of the definitions given to the textual phenomenon because each of them illuminates one or another aspect of the textual phenomenon, that is, certain aspects of the object under study are expressed in each observation. When considering the components of the text and its structural structure, one should not limit oneself to its grammatical analysis (grammar of the text). It is known that low-level parsing operations are not always compatible with text parsing. The communicative relations of speech

acts (actions) should be reflected in the structure of the text. When considering the components of the text and its structural structure, one should not limit oneself to its grammatical analysis (grammar of the text). It is known that low-level parsing operations are not always compatible with text parsing. The communicative relations of speech acts (actions) should be reflected in the structure of the text. When considering the components of the text and its structural structure, one should not limit oneself to its grammatical analysis (grammar of the text). It is known that low-level parsing operations are not always compatible with text parsing. The communicative relations of speech acts (actions) should be reflected in the structure of the text.

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